

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN VISUAL ART CLASSES

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Annotation: This article is about the formation of creative competence of students in visual arts classes, the importance and tasks of forming students' compositional thinking skills in school visual arts classes, and the formation of compositional thinking skills is described in detail.

Key words: visual arts, creativity, competence, compositional thinking.

Introduction:

Art is the expression of events in nature and society in artistic images. Art reflects the general state of the material world, as well as its formation, and serves as a powerful factor in political, moral, and artistic education of a person. Art is divided into such types as fine art, architecture, literature, music, circus, theater, cinema, radio and television, according to the way of expressing reality, character, and essence.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The positive and main feature of art is that, unlike science, it expresses events not in concepts, but in forms perceived by intuition and feeling, in typical artistic images. Art fully expresses the good intentions of mankind, their dreams and hopes. Therefore, as much as our nation respects and respects its art, the nations of the world also look at Uzbek art with such sincerity and respect.

Visual art lessons in general education schools are considered to be the main means of learning aesthetic education, art and culture, history of Uzbek art, and are of great importance in educating students to be spiritually mature. In fine art classes, students learn the basics of scientific knowledge, master existence, which has an effective effect on their ideological, mental, moral, and aesthetic education.

Fine art classes are of particular importance in developing students' spiritual outlook and ideological beliefs. It develops the ability to think, visual memory, creative imagination, artistic taste, and aesthetic feeling. Each type of visual art classes taught at the school helps the growth of students' creative abilities, the improvement of their worldview, that is, it improves the personality in all aspects.

Results:

In fine arts classes, students study the processes of drawing, color science, color image, graphics, design, and modeling depending on the object itself. Composition, compositional vision and compositional thinking are important factors in learning these processes. That is why visual art classes teach first of all how to draw and find a compositional solution to an object or situation. Composition and compositional thinking skills are important not only in fine arts classes, but also in human life.

Discussion:

Formation of compositional thinking ability in school visual arts lessons imposes several main tasks on teachers. First of all, to form the ability of students to see and understand the composition, and then to apply this process in the process of description. Teachers in this case, each educational process is carried out step by step. First of all, students are taught the basic concepts of composition. Later, the tasks become more complicated and they are asked to compose compositions and choose optional subjects. This forms the first stages of compositional thinking in students. As the tasks for the students are gradually becoming more complex, the results will also improve.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it is possible to say that with the help of compositional thinking, students develop aesthetic perception, presentation, and aesthetic feeling, as well as the ability to create, understand, and understand works of art. The thinking process is developed, which is considered necessary in the educational process of students, and it is important in improving the processes of comparison, analysis, synthesis, and generalization.

Fine art lessons directly affect the inner world and outlook of students. The ability of compositional thinking is the basis of visual arts classes and helps to see the world in a better, more beautiful way, to understand its more attractive aspects. The ability to think compositionally is important and important for this purpose.

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